

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

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PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

Project Title: **Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training**

Project Number: **101108469**

Topic: **ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP**

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D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

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Abstract

The objective of the document titled 'PreMETS D7.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan' is to outline a robust communication strategy aimed at effectively sharing the project's objectives and outcomes with the European community. This strategy involves the use of suitable communication materials, various media channels, and targeted events tailored to the intended audience. The document provides a comprehensive overview of the specific actions and steps involved in this communication approach.

The document 'PreMETS D7.1 Communication and dissemination plan' is formulated during an early phase of the project (M3) and addresses the following key aspects while it will be updated at a later point in the project:

- Defining the dissemination goals.
- Identifying the project's primary stakeholders.
- Determining the potential interest groups in the project's outcomes.
- Devising the optimal methods to engage PreMETS stakeholders effectively.
- Establishing ways to measure the efficiency of the awareness raising and dissemination plan.

This document is the first deliverable of Work Package 7 – Impact, Dissemination & Exploitation. This document is designed as a dynamic strategy, allowing for regular updates and enhancements to presented plans as needed during project implementation.

List of PreMETS Participants

Table 1. List of all PreMETS Participants with acronyms

Partner name	Short code
Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	CERTH
Yet Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia	YET
University of Piraeus Research Centre	UPRC
Helixconnect Europe SRL	HELIXCONNECT
Institutul National De Cercetare Dezvoltare In Sudura Si Incercari De Materiale - Isim Timisoara	ISIM
Nano Inteliform SRL	INTEL
EIT Manufacturing East GmbH	EITM
Visokoskolska Ustanova Metropolitanuniverzitet U Beogradu	MUB
Lodzka Izba Przemyslowo-Handlowa	ŁIPH (LCC)
Deep Blue SRL	DEEP BLUE (DB)
ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACC
Foundation Wegemt - A European Association of Universities in Marine Technology and Related Sciences	WEGEMT
Atlantis Engineering AE	ATC

PreMETS Communication Strategy

1. Overview

The PreMETS project has a clear communication strategy to share its goals and results effectively. Various channels like social media, newsletters, and presentations will be used to engage with the project's target groups. Using simple language and visuals will make PreMETS messages easy to understand. Regular updates will keep everyone informed about the project progress, and feedback will be considered to improve upon the ongoing efforts. The communication strategy aim is to connect with people, inspire interest, and create a positive impact through clear and open communication.

2. Description of WP7

The Impact, Dissemination & Exploitation work package focuses on maximizing the positive effects of the project, sharing project results with a wide audience, and ensuring the utilisation of project outcomes for lasting benefits. This work package recognizes that a project's success goes beyond its technical accomplishments and extends into its influence on various stakeholders, sectors, and regions. All PreMETS partners under the coordination of EITM will communicate and disseminate the project promotion and results to a wide range of target groups including the public, making use of a set of target-group adapted and tailor-made communication tools.

3. Objectives of WP7

This Work Package aims to ensure the effectiveness and long-term viability of PreMETS. Its specific goals include:

- Enhancing project visibility and demonstrating the extent of its impact through project activities.
- Spreading expertise and project excellence beyond the project consortium, encompassing a broader scale.
- Identifying connections with related projects, sharing knowledge to enhance impact sustainability.
- Improving the facilitation of the quadruple helix participatory engagement process and foresight exercises.
- Actively shaping policy and contributing to regional development.
- Achieving impact at institutional, regional, national, and international levels.
- Formalizing and institutionalizing each component of the PreMETS platform.
- Developing a 10-year sustainability strategy for the PreMETS platform, along with securing necessary resources (both tangible and intangible).

4. List of Deliverables for WP7

Table 2. List of Deliverables for WP7

	Deliverable title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (In months)
D7.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	EITM	R — Document, report	Public	3
D7.2	Project visual identity pack	YET	Website, filing, videos	Public	3
D7.3	Mailing lists	YET	DEC – data sets, microdata, etc	Sensitive	36
D7.4	Newsletters & fliers	YET	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	Public	36
D7.5	Storytelling videos	YET	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	Public	36
D7.6	Policy briefings	HELIX CONNECT	R — Document, report	Public	36
D7.7	Open day events	HELIX CONNECT	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	36
D7.8	Media outlet events	YET	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	Public	36
D7.9	Impact measurement plan with a preliminary impact assessment	Deep Blue	R — Document, report	Public	36
D7.10	PreMETS 10-year sustainability & commercialization plan	HELIX CONNECT	R — Document, report	Public	36

5. Deliverables Description

Table 3. Deliverables Description

Deliverable	Description
D7.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan	50 pages at the end of the project
D7.2: Project visual identity pack	Project website (translation into EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB.). Project logo and visual themes/guidelines social media accounts setup.
D7.3: Mailing lists	A full (decentralized) mailing list with qualified contacts from each project partner (GDPR compliant) of at least 10,000 contacts.
D7.4: Newsletters & fliers	6 newsletters in English (digital) with limited printed version (600) distributed to at least 10,000 contacts: in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB.
D7.5: Storytelling videos	6 videos developed and disseminated to 20,000 contacts. Videos will be in English with subtitles in RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB.
D7.6: Policy briefings	2 policy briefings (15 pages each) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB.
D7.7: Open day events	8 open day dissemination events will be hosted by (all) partners.
D7.8: Media outlet events	At least 6 appearances in TV/radio/conventional media will be produced.
D7.9: Impact measurement plan with a preliminary impact assessment	Impact assessment report (40 pages in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB).
D7.10: PreMETS 10-year sustainability & commercialization plan	One report (20 pages) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NL, SRB.

6. Timeline of WP7

Table 4. Timeline for deliverables of WP7 Impact, Dissemination, Exploitation

Task	Deliv.	Title	Q	M	Task lead	Participants
Task 7.1	D7.1	Communication and Dissemination plan	Q1	M3 = End of September 23	EITM	EITM
Task 7.2	D7.2 D7.3	Communication infrastructures	Q1	M3 = End of September 23 M36 = End of June 26	YET	CERTH, UPI, HELIX, ISIM, INTEL, EITM, MUB, LCC, DBB, ACC, WEG, ATC
Task 7.3	D7.4 D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	Communication and Dissemination activities	Q1- Q4(3)	M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36 = End of June 26 M36 = End of June 26	EITM	CERTH, YET, UPI, HELIX, ISIM, INTEL, MUB, LCC, DB, ACC, WEG, ATC
Task 7.4	D7.9	Impact measurement plan	Q1, Q3(3), Q4(3)	M3 = End of September 23 M36 = End of June 26	DB	CERTH, YET, UPI, HELIX, ISIM, INTEL, EITM, MUB, LCC, ACC, WEG, ATC
Task 7.5	D7.10	10-year sustainability plan	Q4(3)	M36 = End of June 26	HELIX	CERTH, YET, UPI, ISIM, INTEL, EITM, MUB, LCC, DB, ACC, WEG, ATC

Communication & Dissemination Infrastructure

The following communication & dissemination infrastructure will be developed:

1. Website

- **Audience:** all target groups (Government/Public Sector, Academia/Education Sector, Industry/Private Sector and Civil Society/Community)
- **Objectives:** maintain an online “business card” and provide access to all content and materials developed in the project.
- **Channels:** all project partners will link the website to their institutional profiles. Similarly, the website will be listed in all outputs of PreMETS.
- **Posting frequency:** weekly posts.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: **5,000** website views.
- **Lead:** YET will develop the website.

2. Mailing List

- **Audience:** all target groups that subscribed to the list (GDPR compliance).
- **Objectives:** provide regular updates (monthly) about the project activities, send invitations to and follow-ups from the project events.
- **Channels:** each partner will relay the news via their own institutional mailing list base (GDPR compliant) to maximize the impact.
- **Posting frequency:** monthly communications.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: **10,000** contacts reached.
- Each partner will rely on their internal GDPR-approved mailing lists to maximize dissemination and maintain a close connection with their contacts.
- **Lead:** YET will oversee the mailing list.

3. Digital Leaflet/Flyers

- **Audience:** participants in open day events, virtual pilots, and participants at other conferences/events where PreMETS will be represented.

- **Objectives:** to disseminate static content from the project to an audience that is not familiar yet with PreMETS. This will ensure raising awareness and engagement to the project activities.
- **Channels:** each activity organizer will distribute them during the respective events.
- **Posting frequency:** every 3 months.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: **10,000** contacts reached with at least 6 newsletters.
- **Lead:** YET will provide the templates while CERTH, HELIX, ISIM, MUB, LCC and ACC will be leading the development of the 6 newsletters (with contribution from all partners).

4. Storytelling via Promotional Videos

After the pilots, a series of interviews will be carried out (with learners, trainers, and industries), these will be presented as short stories from trainers on “why” and the “added value” of PreMETS outputs for the target groups. Similarly, **short promotional videos will be produced (shorter videos recommended, -1 minute)**, presenting briefly and in an appealing way the outputs of PreMETS.

- **Audience:** all target groups.
- **Objectives:** to introduce the PreMETS spirit and raise awareness of its importance, while positioning PreMETS as a key enabler of predictive maintenance provider for online education.
- **Channels:** each project partners will deliver the testimonials through their international channels.
- **Posting frequency:** every 3 months in the second half of the project.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: 20,000 contacts reached with at least 6 videos.
- **Lead:** The pilot organizers (UPI & ISIM) will oversee the videos with the support of YET.

5. Social Media

- **Audience:** all target groups.
- **Objectives:** Relay weekly updates from the project, promote events and engage the target groups into the project activities.

- **Channels:** LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Facebook and YouTube will be utilized as the main social media networks for disseminating PreMETS outputs and for maintaining the community (i.e., the alumni network).
- **Posting frequency:** weekly posts.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: 100,000 interactions on social media.
- **Lead:** YET will develop the social media accounts while EITM will coordinate the communication strategy.

6. Policy Briefings & PreMETS Open Days

- **Audience:** participants in the open day events both physically and online.
- **Objectives:** to ensure that the project outputs are communicated to the target groups
- **Channels:** each activity organizer will convey these messages during each open day event while also developing targeted policy briefings and asking the stakeholders for engagement and co-creation for further validating the outputs.

- **Posting frequency:** 8 open day events organized in the second half of the project. The open days consist of 1-day mini-conferences in each PreMETS country (100 blended attendees per event) that will have the chance to test the PreMETS platform and its educational offer while engaging with key targets from each country.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: At least 20 policy makers reached and 800 participants in the open days reached.
- **Lead:** HELIX will oversee coordinating the open days while CERTH, ISIM, EITM, MUB, ACC, DB, WEG and LCC will oversee hosting one open day

Table 5. Policy Briefings & PreMETS Open Days

Event No.	Participant	Name	Type	Area	Location	Duration (in days)	Total attendees
E7.1	CERTH	Open day 1	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Thessaloniki, Greece	1	100
E7.2	ISIM	Open day 2	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Timisuara, Romania	1	100
E7.3	EITM	Open day 3	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Vienna, Austria	1	100
E7.4	MUB	Open day 4	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Belgrade, Serbia	1	100
E7.5	LCC	Open day 5	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Lodz, Poland	1	100
E7.6	DB	Open day 6	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Rome, Italy	1	100
E7.7	ACC	Open day 7	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Nicosia, Cyprus	1	100
E7.8	WEG	Open day 8	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Amsterdam, NE	1	100

- Each of the open day organizers will rely on their networks to engage the audience and policy makers.
- Two policy briefings will be issued (under the coordination of EITM).

7. Paid Ads & Promotion During the Work Based Learning Pilots

- **Audience:** learners & trainers primarily.
- **Objectives:** to ensure targeted communication of PreMETS outputs directly to the main target groups in a personalized manner to boost engagement and foster recruitment for the PreMETS Platform.
- **Channels:** paid ads on social media and promotion during the pilots.

- **Posting frequency:** every 6 months.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: at least 1,000 qualified contacts reached and engaged in the platform.
- **Lead:** YET will organize the paid ad campaigns while partners will take rotations in the implementation.

8. Media Outlet Promotion (TV, Radio)

- **Audience:** all target groups (and more traditional local/regional actors such as vet (Vocational Education and Training programs) providers and companies including social groups at risk)
- **Objectives:** to ensure inclusive communication of PreMETS outputs directly to the main target groups to boost awareness and recruitment for the PreMETS Platform (every 6 months).
- **Channels:** TV and Radio outlets (commitment letters available).
- **Posting frequency:** every 3 months in the second half of the project.
- **KPI:** at the end of the project: at least 6 appearances reaching a general audience of at least 1,000,000 citizens.
- **Lead:** YET, HELIX, EITM and LCC will particularly oversee the outlet promotion strategy while the other partners will contribute.

Specific Tasks and Description

Table 6. Specific Tasks and Description

Task	Description
T7.1 Communication & Dissemination plan:	To facilitate effective communication and dissemination throughout PreMETS, a structured Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) is established. This plan is crucial due to the project's emphasis on external participatory engagement and citizen science, creating continuous opportunities for dissemination and communication at each project stage.
T7.2 Communication & Dissemination infrastructure and networks:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Branding: YET will develop the logo, guidelines, and graphical designs. 2. Templates: YET will create templates for documents, presentations, posters, etc. 3. Communication Materials: Templates for leaflets, posters, presentations, roll-up banners, business cards, infographics,

	<p>newsletters, videos, and advertising materials will be provided by YET, while content will come from all partners.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Social Media: YET will set up LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Facebook and YouTube accounts, and all partners will contribute to creating templates. 5. Coordination: YET will oversee the entire process. 6. Design and Content Impact: HELIXCONNECT will ensure overall design and content adhere to cross-cutting considerations, including target group behavior, EU visual guidelines, industrial professional standards, citizen science, and research communication in plain language.
<p>T7.3 Communication & Dissemination activities:</p>	<p>The activities outlined in Section 3.2 will be executed, with the use of altimetric tools for monitoring conversations. This enables ongoing strategy evaluation and adaptation throughout the project. Content will primarily be in English for international audiences but will also be localized and translated into national languages as needed.</p>
<p>T7.4 Impact measurement plan:</p>	<p>To achieve and measure impact, PreMETS will implement an impact measurement methodology, integrating quality, monitoring, dissemination, and progress activities throughout the project timeline. Specific metrics will be used to measure and monitor each defined impact, ensuring credible evidence-based impact measurement. The development of this plan will be overseen by Deep Blue.</p>
<p>T7.5 PreMETS platform 10- year sustainability & commercialization plan:</p>	<p>HELIX will spearhead this task, coordinating sustainability and commercialization activities. PreMETS will be leveraged through a joint venture with all partners to create shared value and engage all stakeholders. The commercialization and post-project exploitation plan includes a 6-step strategy aimed at generating revenue and enhancing the platform. This plan will be both developed and put into action.</p>

Summary of Key Performance Indicators of WP7

- **Website:** 5,000 views by month 36.
- **Mailing list:** 10,000 contacts by month 36.
- **Digital Leaflets/ flyers:** 10,000 contacts reached with at least 6 newsletters by month 36.

- **Storytelling via promotional videos:** 20,000 contacts reached with at least 6 videos by month 36.
- **Social media channels:** LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Facebook and YouTube: 100,000 interactions on social media by month 36.
- **Policy briefings and PreMETS open days:** At least 20 policy makers reached and 800 participants in the open days reached by month 36.
- **Paid ads and promotion during the work-based learning pilots:** at least 1,000 qualified contacts reached and engaged in the platform by month 36.
- **Media outlet promotion (tv, radio):** at least 6 appearances reaching a general audience of at least 1,000,000 citizens by month 36.

Management of Impact, Dissemination, and Exploitation strategy

All partners play an active role in making sure the project's goals are shared widely and its results are effectively communicated. Partners are expected to use their connections and networks to reach the intended audiences, promote the project within their own countries, contribute to the project's social media accounts with updates from their regions or sectors, attend relevant events to showcase the project and its achievements, and create communication materials that align with the project's visual guidelines. This collaborative effort will help achieve successful project dissemination and communication.

- Various tools and resources for communication and dissemination will be developed. This includes creating project branding elements i.e., the logo and design guidelines, as well as templates for documents, presentations, and other communication materials such as leaflets, posters, presentations, videos, and more will have templates designed by YET while content will be contributed by all partners.
- Social media accounts (LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Facebook, YouTube) managed by YET and using templates/input from partners will be established. YET will coordinate this process, ensuring the design and content align with important

considerations like target audience behaviour, EU visual guidelines, industry standards, citizen science, and clear communication. All partners will provide content, each month will be a partner's responsibility to create four posts to be published on all PreMETS channels. A folder is created on the GD within WP7 titled (Social Media Content) where all partners can access and add text and images so that YET can publish them accordingly.

- The communication and dissemination activities will be implemented, using tools to monitor conversations. This ongoing evaluation will help to adjust our strategy as needed during the project timeline.
- While most content will be in English for international audiences, important materials will also be translated into national languages when necessary.
- All PreMETS partners consider that beyond promotion actions, active engagement is necessary to ensure enough participation of companies and other value chain stakeholders in the project.

Target Audience

- Academics
- Vocational learners
- Other employees working in manufacturing

Internal Communication

The internal communication strategy focuses on maximizing interaction and knowledge transfer between partners. PreMETS will deploy a set of tools to maximize the effectiveness and efficiency of internal communication and collaboration, including:

- a) Online secure intranet featuring project and file management tools – dedicated project's cloud, available only for the partners.

- b) Appropriate team mailing lists – contact list created by the EITM and uploaded on the project's folder. [Link](#)
- c) Teleconferencing and video conferencing systems – MS Teams.
- d) Monthly meetings.
- e) Templates – to facilitate the communication, document, deliverables, and presentation templates will be created.

Visual Identity and Branding

1. PreMETS Project Identity

A brand identity serves as a distinguishing feature for the project among other projects. It encompasses the project's personality, core attributes, concepts, and visual elements. The primary objective is to establish a polished and enduring professional image for the project, one that can function as a recognizable brand throughout its lifespan, encompassing both the project's duration and the long-term utilization of its outcomes.

The creation of the project's identity was driven by the intention of streamlining communication, dissemination, and engagement while bolstering the project's visibility. This project identity serves as the foundation for all instances and representations of the project, spanning its website, promotional materials, publications, social media presence, and video content.

2. Logo

As an initial milestone, the establishment of PreMETS' visual identity was meticulously crafted during the project's inaugural two months, with the explicit aim of ensuring the project's immediate recognition. This distinctive logo will be prominently featured in all project-related communications, serving as a clear and obvious identifier.

PreMETS visual identity will be seamlessly integrated into all materials generated within the project's framework, including presentation templates, project documents, flyers, roll-up banners, website content, social media profiles, and video productions. To achieve this, three preliminary versions of PreMETS' logo were developed, drawing inspiration from proposals submitted by consortium partners.

The logo design tried to encapsulate the essence of Predictive Maintenance and the mission of the PreMETS project. It's a visual representation of progress, trust, and innovation in the world of maintenance and technology. The project partners believe

this logo will leave a lasting impression and resonate with the target audience, furthering the goals of the project.

Through a democratic voting process within the consortium, the ultimate iteration of the official partnership logo was chosen.

The main version of the logo is presented with the colour palette:

- #0462EF
- #15E99B
- #000000
- #191919
- #ffffff

PreMETS logos:

Logo Concept:**Icon: [The Abstract Soundwave](#)**

The icon, an abstract soundwave, is a perfect representation of Acoustic Analysis Monitoring – one of the key methods of Predictive Maintenance. It visually signifies the data and information extracted from machinery sounds, which plays a vital role in maintaining equipment health. The dynamic and flowing form of the soundwave symbolizes the continuous monitoring and real-time analysis that are at the heart of Predictive Maintenance.

Colour Palette: [Light Green and Blue](#)

- **Light Green:** This colour represents growth, innovation, and sustainability. It's the colour of progress, indicating how Predictive Maintenance fosters sustainable development by reducing downtime and resource wastage.
- **Blue:** Blue signifies trust, reliability, and technology. It symbolizes the dependable nature of Predictive Maintenance in ensuring machinery operates smoothly and efficiently.

Typography:

Calibri is selected as the primary font for text and Apros is the secondary font to be used in communication within the consortium, e.g., in documents, emails, etc. because it's clean, modern, and highly legible. Its geometric shapes reflect precision, which aligns

with the accuracy and efficiency inherent in Predictive Maintenance. The use of a consistent font creates a harmonious balance between the icon and the project name. The official font used on the PreMETS website: Google font – Open Sans, alternative font: Google fonts – Arimo.

Overall Justification:

The logo design is a visual testament to the core values and objectives of the PreMETS project:

- **Innovation:** The abstract soundwave icon represents cutting-edge technology and the innovative approach of Predictive Maintenance.
- **Sustainability:** The light green colour signifies the project's commitment to sustainable practices in maintenance.
- **Reliability:** The blue colour instils trust, emphasizing the reliability of Predictive Maintenance in ensuring equipment longevity.

EU Co-Branding: **Visibility — European flag and funding statement**

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Co-funded by the
European Union

Co-funded by the
European Union

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Offline Tools

1. Flyer, roll-up, project presentation, posters

A flyer, poster, project presentation template (MS Power Point), reports/ deliverables template (MS Word) and a roll-up banner will be designed in M3. These materials will contain overall information as a brief description of PreMETS, its objectives and opportunities. The flyer will exist in electronic form to be forwarded via e-mail and downloaded from the website; furthermore, there will be printed versions to be used for conferences and physical events. The roll-up will be used also during all physical events, as well as a general presentation of the project and poster. Production of those promotional materials will allow potentially interested stakeholders and the public to be informed about PreMETS.

2. Press Release and Articles

Information about the project, open calls, its activities, and results will be disseminated through press releases. These press releases will be meticulously crafted and dispatched to both mainstream and specialized media outlets. Partners will have the flexibility to customize the content to align with their corporate messaging and spread it through their respective communication channels. In a broader context, every partner is expected to incorporate the project's logo alongside their own logo if deemed necessary. Any usage of another partner's logo in publications must be approved by the respective partner beforehand.

3. Events

Consortium partners will represent the project at international, regional, or local events (congresses, seminars, conferences, workshops, and fairs) to promote the project objectives and results.

4. Partners Reporting Dashboard

To monitor all the dissemination activities carried out by PreMETS partners, EITM will create the partners actions reporting dashboard, an excel sheet available online on the project's internal SharePoint. It will include dedicated tabs to report press clippings, posts on social media, publications, attendant of events, etc.

The tool has two main purposes:

- Monitor all dissemination and communication activities going on within the project.
- To keep track of all events that partners are attending and they are promoting the project.

Partners will be requested to update the dashboard by adding the activities they carry out. The Communication Manager will regularly check the dashboard and refresh the progress of the specific KPIs to make a close monitoring on dissemination efforts.

PreMETS Materials

Templates will be developed during the first three months of PreMETS project kick off. YET as the task leader prepared templates to be used by the consortium in all communication and dissemination activities. They have been designed in line with the project's visual identity.

Two templates were prepared:

- a. Deliverable/ Document template (see Annex 1)
- b. Presentation template (see Annex 2)

All templates are available for all partners on a dedicated WP7 Communication and dissemination folder in the project's internal SharePoint.